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Abstract

Learners whose social identity is defined by minority group memberships may become demotivated when there is a lack of equity in the curriculum. This workshop explores two barriers to equity in music education for students in low-income areas and racialized students; these students are marginalized due to a lack of resources and a lack of representation in the curriculum respectively. We will discuss the impact of the lack of representation and resources in music education on the engagement, achievement and well-being of Black students in the Jane and Finch area. We will then explore how to source instruments for music programs and integrate pan-African music into the music curricula of schools and community music programs. This is necessary as all children need resources to excel, and children of pan-African descent need positive representations of themselves, beyond tokenism, to promote their success and well-being.